

Mixed ligand complexes of nickel-, copper- and zinc(II) with 5-chloro(or bromo)salicylaldehyde and hydroxyaromatic aldehydes or ketones

R. N. Prasad*, Mithlesh Agrawal and Remesh George

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, India

E-mail : prasadragnandan@yahoo.com

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Mixed ligand complexes of the types $[M(L)(L')]$ and $[Ni(L)(L')(H_2O)_2]$ (where $M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$; $HL = 5\text{-chlorosalicylaldehyde}$, $HL' = \text{salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone or 2-hydroxypropionophenone}$; $HL = 5\text{-chloro(or bromo)salicylaldehyde}$, $HL' = 2\text{-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-hydroxybenzophenone}$) have been synthesized and characterized by conductances, TLC, thermal analyses, magnetic moments, IR, 1H NMR and electronic spectral studies.

In continuation of our earlier communication¹, synthesis and characterisation of mixed ligand complexes of the types $[M(L)(L')]$ and $[Ni(L)(L')(H_2O)_2]$ (where $M = Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$; $HL = 5\text{-chlorosalicylaldehyde (5-ClSal)}$, $HL' = \text{salicylaldehyde (sal), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hap) or 2-hydroxypropionophenone (hpp)}$; $HL = 5\text{-chloro(or bromo)salicylaldehyde (5-Cl or Brsal)}$, $HL' = 2\text{-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (hnp) or 2-hydroxybenzophenone (hbzp)}$) are described in the present paper.

Results and discussion

The reactions of Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} chlorides with 5-chloro(or bromo)salicylaldehyde and salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropionophenone, 2-hydroxybenzophenone or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of mixed ligand complexes $[MLL']$ ($M = Cu^{II}$ or Zn^{II}) and $[NiLL'(H_2O)_2]$. The Ni^{II} complexes are green, Cu^{II} complexes are grey and Zn^{II} complexes are yellow solids. They are insoluble in organic solvents such as benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, methanol and nitrobenzene, but soluble in DMSO. The characteristics and analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. Molar conductances of the complexes are very low indicating their non-electrolytic nature². In TLC, all the mixed ligand complexes show single spots with R_f values being intermediate of the two corresponding symmetrical bis-complexes indicating that these are mixed ligand complexes rather than a mixture of the two corresponding bis-complexes.

Infrared spectra : The mixed ligand complexes reveal strong absorption bands at $1590\text{--}1645\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to coordinated $C=O$ group. These bands are at lower wave numbers as compared to those in the free ligands, supporting the

coordination of $C=O$ group to the metal atom^{3,4}. Weak to medium intensity bands at $400\text{--}525\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are absent in the free ligands, may be attributed to $\nu(M-O)$ vibration⁴.

Thermal analysis : Thermograms of Ni^{II} complexes exhibit weight loss in the region $120\text{--}180^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to two coordinated H_2O molecules. This is confirmed by the sharp endothermic peak observed in the region $120\text{--}220^\circ\text{C}$ in the DTA curves of Ni^{II} complexes. TGA and DTA studies confirm the absence of coordinated water molecules in Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} mixed ligand complexes.

Magnetic moment : The μ_{eff} values (at $\sim 300\text{ K}$) for Cu^{II} complexes (1.70–2.25 B.M.) are in the range expected for a d^9 system. Slightly higher values may be due to the incomplete quenching of the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment⁵ or due to spin-orbit coupling⁶. The μ_{eff} values in the range 1.80–2.10 B.M. have been reported for bis- and mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 2-hydroxybenzophenone^{4,7}. For Ni^{II} complexes, the μ_{eff} values are observed in the range 2.66–3.31 B.M., suggesting distorted octahedral geometry. The μ_{eff} values higher than the spin only value (2.83 B.M.) may be due to orbital contribution from 3T excited state⁸. The μ_{eff} values in the range 2.87–3.43 B.M. have been reported for octahedral bis- and mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and 2-hydroxybenzophenone^{3,4}. Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

Electronic spectra : In the electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes, a broad absorption band centered at $649\text{--}700\text{ nm}$ ($\epsilon = 15\text{--}104$) suggests a square planar geometry and rules out the possibility of tetrahedral geometry⁹. This band does not show any sign of splitting suggesting that all the expected

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the mixed ligand complexes

Compd.	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Metal (%):		Molar conduct. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
		Found	(Calcd.)		
[Ni(5-ClSal)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	178–182	15.71	(15.81)	11	3.08
[Ni(5-ClSal)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂]	168–174	15.32	(15.23)	18	3.30
[Ni(5-ClSal)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	180–185	14.80	(14.70)	13	3.11
[Ni(5-ClSal)(hbzp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	160–166	13.20	(13.13)	19	3.31
[Ni(5-ClSal)(hnp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	238–243	13.89	(13.93)	10	2.74
[Ni(5-Brsal)(hnp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	341–346	12.58	(12.60)	11	2.66
[Ni(5-Brsal)(hbzp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	178–184	11.86	(11.94)	21	2.82
[Cu(5-ClSal)(sal)]	252–255	18.75	(18.69)	4	2.25
[Cu(5-ClSal)(hap)]	238–242	17.98	(17.95)	9	2.08
[Cu(5-ClSal)(hpp)]	245–248	17.35	(17.27)	13	2.14
[Cu(5-ClSal)(hbzp)]	160–166	15.31	(15.27)	7	2.06
[Cu(5-ClSal)(hnp)]	175–180	16.21	(16.29)	9	2.25
[Cu(5-Brsal)(hnp)]	126–132	14.52	(14.63)	12	1.83
[Cu(5-Brsal)(hbzp)]	265–268	13.71	(13.80)	15	1.70
[Zn(5-ClSal)(sal)]	280–285	19.24	(19.12)	23	Diamag.
[Zn(5-ClSal)(hap)]	275–280	18.48	(18.37)	21	Diamag.
[Zn(5-ClSal)(hpp)]	290–295	17.74	(17.68)	18	Diamag.
[Zn(5-ClSal)(hbzp)]	298–304	15.58	(15.64)	16	Diamag.
[Zn(5-ClSal)(hnp)]	220–225	16.71	(16.68)	9	Diamag.
[Zn(5-Brsal)(hnp)]	172–178	14.87	(14.98)	14	Diamag.
[Zn(5-Brsal)(hbzp)]	246–251	14.04	(14.14)	24	Diamag.

d-d transitions are lying within this broad band¹⁰. Similar results have been reported for bis- and mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-hydroxybenzophenone^{4,7}. In case of Ni^{II} complexes, a weak band at 693–717 nm ($\epsilon = 13\text{--}53$) may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3I_{1g}(F)$ transition. The band due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition merges with the charge transfer band at 436–449 nm ($\epsilon = 477\text{--}684$). These observed transitions are in the range required for octahedral nickel(II) complexes⁹. Similar results have been reported for octahedral bis- and mixed ligand complexes of Ni^{II} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-hydroxybenzophenone^{3,4}. In all the complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}, strong absorption bands at 311–327 nm ($\epsilon = 293\text{--}551$) and at ~370 nm ($\epsilon = 253\text{--}492$) may be due to intra-ligand transitions ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$ or $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) and the band at 408–454 nm ($\epsilon = 359\text{--}684$) may be charge transfer band.

¹H NMR spectra : In the ¹H NMR spectra of mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II}, singlet due to the CH proton of the aldehyde residues and triplet of CH₃ and quartet of CH₂ protons of propiophenone residue are shifted upfield, confirming the coordination of C=O group of these ligands to zinc atom. The disappearance of the signal due to the

OH proton of the ligands in the mixed ligand complexes confirms the coordination of phenolic oxygen to the zinc with loss of proton.

Experimental

5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxybenzophenone (all Aldrich) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka) were recrystallized from hot ethanol. Salicylaldehyde (Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (Boehringer), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (Fluka) and ethanol were purified by distillation. NiCl₂·6H₂O, CuCl₂·2H₂O and ZnCl₂ (all Fluka) were of A.R. grade.

Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were determined by standard methods¹¹. TLC of the complexes was performed on silica gel G using benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°C) (1 : 1) as the mobile phase and the spots on the TLC plates were detected by iodine vapours. Specific conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were measured at room temperature on a Systronics 304 instrument using a glass cell having cell constant 1.0 cm⁻¹. Magnetic moments were measured on Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as calibrant. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet

Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (DMSO) on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Zeol FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer at 90 MHz using TMS as an internal standard. Thermal studies (TGA and DTA) were carried out on a RIGAKU Thermoflex PTC 10A TG DTA instrument under nitrogen atmosphere at the heating rate of $10^\circ/\text{min}$.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes : To the ethanolic solution of Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} chloride (2.81 mmol in ~ 10 ml ethanol), an ethanolic solution of two different carbonyl compounds (2.81 mmol each in ~ 10 ml ethanol) was added with stirring. A clear solution was obtained. The pH of the reaction mixture was raised to ~ 5.5 by adding 5% aq. NaOH. Stirring was continued for 3–4 h and the solid products formed were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

The Zn^{II} mixed ligand complexes were prepared similarly except using aq. ammonia solution in place of aq. NaOH.

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References

1. R. N. Prasad, M. Agrawal and M. Sharma, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 559; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 531; *J. Serb. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **67**, 229; R. N. Prasad, M. Agrawal and R. George, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 79.
2. W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
3. D. P. Graddon and G. M. Mockler, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 21.
4. S. I. Mustafa, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1998, **23**, 397; P. Athappan and G. Rajagopal, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1997, **22**, 840; V. B. Mohankumar and P. K. Bhattacharya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 132.
5. B. N. Figgis and C. M. Harris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 855.
6. A. E. Earnshaw, "Introduction to Magnetochemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 35.
7. D. P. Graddon and G. M. Mockler, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, **21**, 617.
8. W. F. Currier and J. A. Webber, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1539.
9. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, New York, 1986.
10. F. A. Cotton and J. J. Wise, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 917.
11. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Longman, London, 1961.